

AFFIXATION AS WORD FORMATION PROCESS IN ENGLISH CONTRASTIVE WITH ALBANIAN

Morphology

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Abstract

Learning a new language sometimes is fun but sometimes it becomes a real challenge. Grammatical rules play an important role in learning a foreign language. If people lack knowledge about the grammatical part that a language possesses, they will never be capable to communicate or write in that language without making grammar mistakes and that's a serious issue! The main aim discussed in this study is a detailed analysis of the affixation as a word formation process in English and Albanian language as well. Grammar is one of the most important parts in every language of the world. Through grammar there is cohesion and coherence in sentences and texts. Each language has its own characteristics that make that language unique. The methodology of this study is mostly comparative and descriptive where similarities and differences about affixation as a word formation process in both languages are highlighted and all the features are clarified in a simple way by definitions and examples for each.

Theoretical Approach

There are many researches about word formation processes, especially for affixation. Some of the previous studies about affixation are: According to Agalliu, Angoni, Demiraj, Dhrimo, Hysa, & Likaj, (2002: 61), “*Prejardhje quket formimi i fjalëve të reja me anë të bashkimit të ndajshesave fjalëformuese me tema fjalësh ose me fjalë, sipas modeleve të fjalëformimit që ekzistojnë në gjuhë*”. According to Ibrahimimi, S., & Iseni, A. (2008: 60), “*The morphemes that precede the root (like en- in enlarge) are called **prefixes**, while those that follow it are called **suffixes** (like –ance in performance, –ness in whiteness, and –able in readable). An umbrella term for prefixes and suffixes (broadly speaking, for all morphemes that are not roots) is **affix***”. After all the gathered definitions, my own definition about affixation would be: “*Affixation is a word formation process of making new words by adding affixes to the root or the base word.*”

Introduction

Every language in the world has its own characteristics, functions and usage. In every language except differences there are still many similarities. These differences and similarities are also found in the grammar part. Morphology is one of the most important branches of a language. In linguistics, morphology is the study of the forms of words, from the Greek word *morphe* that means *shape* or *form*. Morphology is used to denote the study of words, both with regard to their internal structure and their combination or formation to form new or larger units. The smallest units of language that have a meaning or a grammatical function and form words or part of words are called morphemes. Morphemes are grouped into free and bound morphemes. Linguists have

identified many ways in which English form its words which include borrowing from Latin and Greek, clipping, affixation, conversion, acronyms, blending, compounding and so on.

Introduction of Affixation in English

Affixation is a word formation process of making new words by adding affixes to the root or base word. “If the new word is formed by the combination of prefix and the base, the process involved is called prefixation or prefixing e.g. **unkind, disagree, and misbehave**. If the new word is formed by the combination of a base and a suffix, the process involved is called suffixation e.g. **kindness, modernize, friendly**”.¹ “There are encountered far more suffixes than prefixes, and this is not an accident: there are indeed more suffixes than prefixes in English”.² According to last researches, over 80% of the total vocabulary of English is borrowed and most of its words can be used with affixation. Furthermore, using affixation strategies helps learners naturally expand their knowledge of meaning or grammatical categories.

Prefixation in English

Prefixation is a word formation process where the bound morpheme is added to the front of a root or stem. The prefixes in English are mostly prepositions and adverbs. The most productive prefixes can be considered as below:

Post-, pre-, multi-, poly-

Postage, postgraduate, pre-war, pre-test, prepaid, preview, multi-lateral, multimillionaire, policlinic. When some prefixes are added to the word, they give the existing word the negative or the opposite meaning.

E.g. *un-, anti-, dis-, mis-*

Unkind, unpopular, unlock, undo, unhappy, unfriendly, unfair, antiabortion, anti-climax, antisocial, antibody, disbelief, disappear, discredits, disagree, disapprove, dissatisfied, disability, misunderstanding, misbehave, mistake.

non-, im-, ir-, in-

non-admission, non-aggression, non-specialist, impossible, impatient, imperfect, impolite, irregular, irrelevant, irrational, irresponsible, injustice, incorrect, independent, indefinite.

¹ Jashar Kabashi. *English Grammar Morphology*. (Prishtinë, 2000), p. 362.

² Sami Ibrahim & Arburim Iseni. *Modern English Grammar*. (Tetovë, 2008), p. 60.

Ill-, bi-, co-, re-,

Illegal, illegible, illegitimate, illiberal, bilingual, bicycle, bilateral, co-founder, cooperate, co-pilot, co-author, rename, remove, return, repay, remix,

Out-, super-, under-, de-

Outside, outlook, outdoor, supermarket, superman, superstar, superhero, undersea, underclass, underclothes, under-roof, undervalue, undersecretary, decode, decompose.

Anti-, em-, en-, fore-, inter-,

Antifreeze, antithesis, embrace, emphasis, encode, encounter, forecast, foresight, interact, international, interdisciplinary.

Mid-, non-, over-, pre-,

Midday, midnight, midway, nonsense, non-exist, overlook, overdue, preschool, prefix, overdose, over-anxious, overcharge.

Regain-, semi-, sub-, extra-, sur-, tele-, mono-, mini-

Regain, return, rebuild, semi-final, semi-circle, subeditor, extraordinary, extra-curricular, extramarital, surtax, surcharge, telefax, television, telecommunication, telescope, monotheism, monoacid, minibus etc.

Suffixation in English

English language has suffixes that create new words from bases of names adjective, verbs. The most productive suffixes in English are considered:

- al** – Proposal, approval, arrival, burial, denial, constitutional, racial, betrayal,
- er, -or** – Londoner, villager, banker, tanker, driver, reader, computer, recorder, server, cleaner, dreamer, seller, baker, container, boiler, governor, sailor,
- hood, -dom** – neighbourhood, childhood, boyhood, manhood, motherhood, kingdom, freedom, boredom, wisdom, stardom.
- ician, -ist** – mathematician, politician, pharmacist, artist, biologist, realist, impressionist, scientist, humanist, economist.
- ness** – happiness, kindness, goodness, willingness, usefulness.
- ism** – heroism, nationalism, patriotism, egoism, idealism.
- or** – translator, elector, director, inspector, actor.
- ian, -ant** – comedian, musician, guardian, American, Victorian, servant, inhabitant, solvent.
- ing** – reading, painting, swimming, driving, recording, building.

–**able, –ible** – readable, agreeable, comfortable, preventable, portable, legible,
 –**ry, –ery** – dentistry, chemistry, pedantry, jewellery, slavery, bakery, fishery.
 –**ion, –tion** – occasion, attraction, translation, identification, ratification, foundation,
 organization.

–**ity, –ty** – safety, elasticity, diversity, readability.

–**age** – package, orphanage, mileage, postage, heritage, percentage, stoppage.

–**ship** – relationship, membership, scholarship, friendship, fellowship, hardship.

–**cy –acy** – accuracy, bankruptcy, presidency, privacy, legitimacy, bureaucracy.

–**ment** – treatment, argument, employment, government, arrangement, assessment,
 achievement, agreement.

–**ess** – hostess, baroness, lioness, waitress, actress.

In English, the new words are made from the root and the suffix that changes the grammatical class. The root might be a verb, noun, or adjective that changes the grammatical class when a suffix is added. Some of the examples are provided below:

New words created by suffixes from verb to noun:

Verb to Noun

Improve	improvement
Manage	management
Elect	election
Inform	information
Administer	Administration
Spell	Spelling
Work	worker
Employ	employee
Beg	beggar

Adjective to Noun

Weak	weakness
Dark	darkness
Similar	similarity
Stupid	stupidity

Noun, verbs and adjective with the same root

English language has a lot of words with the same structure (root) but with the suffix has different meaning.

<i>Adjective</i>	<i>verb</i>	<i>noun</i>
Bright	brighten	brightness
Broad	broaden	broadness
Dark	darken	darkness
Deep	deepen	deepness/ depth
Fast	fasten	fastness
Fresh	freshen	freshness
Light	lighten	lightness
Mad	madden	madness
Quick	quicken	quickness
Sad	sadden	sadness
Sharp	sharpen	sharpness
Sick	sicken	sickness
Soft	soften	softness
Thick	thicken	thickness
Tight	tighten	tightness
Sweet	sweeten	sweetness
Weak	weaken	weakness
White	whiten	whiteness
Wide	widen	wideness/ width

Infixation

Infixation is a morphological process whereby a bound morpheme attaches within a root or stem. The kind of affix involved in this process is called an infix. Infixes are inserted within the root stem.

Examples of affixes are:

ABS**O**BLOOMINGL**U**TELY
 M**O**THERS-IN-L**A**W
 SING**A**BLOODY**P**O**R**E
 ABS**O**GOD**D**AML**U**TELY

PASSERS-**B**Y
 FAN**F**LAMING**T**ASTIC
 FAN**B**LOODY**T**ASTIC
 UN**F**UCKING**B**ELIVABLE

Introduction of Affixation in Albanian Language

Affixation is the most productive way in the system of word formation in Albanian language. The formation of new words by adding affixes to the root is called affixation.

“Prejardhje quhet formimi i fjalëve të reja me ndihmën e ndajshesave fjalëformuese që u shtohet fjalëve rrënjë ose fjalëve të tëra të prejardhura. Fjalët e prejardhura formohen duke i shtuar temës fjalëformuese parashtesa, prapashtesa ose të dyja së bashku. Parashtesat vendosen

përpara fjalës rrënjë, ndërsa prapashtesat vendosen pas rrënjës dhenë të shumtën e rasteve, ndryshojnë klasën gramatikore të fjalës bazë.”³

The derivation of prefixes (prejardhja parashtesore)

Prefixation is a way of forming new words from adding prefixes to the existing word. Prefixation doesn't change the grammatical category of the word but it only fulfills or gives a new meaning to that word. E.g. **mosbesim**, **stërgjysh**, i **pavlefshëm**, **çarmatos**, **nënçmoj**.

There are also some words in Albanian that are formed with prefixes and belong to a different word class in comparison to the root or base word.

*E.g. **baltë – përbalt, buzë – përbuz, gjak – përgjak, burrë – mburr, faqe – shfaq.***

Prefixes in Albanian, are one third compared to suffixes and don't have their productivity. But, prefixation plays an important role in word formation process in Albanian language.

A number of prefixes in Albanian are very productive such are:

***sh-, zh-, ç-, m-, n-, stër-, shpër-, pa-, mos-, kundër-, para-, prapa-, nën-, pas-, mbi-, bashkë-, mos-, jo-, ri-, bi-, dy-, super-, larg-, jashtë-, brenda-, lart-, pranë-, sipër-, krye** etc.*

Some of these prefixes make the opposite of the existing word by giving negative meaning.

Some examples with prefixes

Pandërprerë, pakryera, mospërfillje, mosbesim, mosmirënjohje, mosmarrëveshje, jozyrtare, jonormale, jomiqësore, kundërgaz, kundërajror, paralajmërim, paraardhës, paramendim, parandjenjë, prapashtesë, parashtesë, prapambetur, sipërmarrës, sipërfaqe, sipërshënuar, nënpunësim, nënvezhim, pasardhës, pasuniversitare, mbishkrim, mbingarkesë, përmasë, përmirësim, përfytyrim, përgëzim, ndajshitim, ndajfolje, stërgjysh, superfuqi, superhero, ndërldhje, ndërkombëtar, ndërhyrje, bashkëpunim, bashkëatdhetar, bashkëjetesë, bashkëthemelues, joshkencore, jopjellore, çarmatos, shqep, çrregullim, shfajësim, rilexim, rikendim, ripunim, rinisje, rizgjedhje, riorganizim, çbllokoj/zhblllokoj, çvesh/zhvesh, kundërligjshme, mbivlerë, mbikqyrje, mbishpenzim, mbitokë, nëntokë, paralufte, paradite, pasdreke, paradhënie, paracaktim, parapëlqej, parashikoj, i prapambetur, pasthirmë, jashtëshkruaj, brendashkruaj, largpamës, largvajtës, shkurtpamës, bilingual, bilateral, dybrirësh, dyvjeçar, kryeministër, kryevendi, kryevepër etc.

³ Bahri Beci, Gramatika e gjuhës shqipe për të gjithë, Prishtinë, 2001, p.34.

Albanian language is enriched with some foreign prefixes such are:

a-, anti-, de-, dez-, dis-, pro-, pan-, trans-, ultra-, multi-, ekstra etc.

Some examples about each:

Anormal, **d**ezinfektoj, **d**isharmoni, **a**fetar, **a**ntikombëtar, **a**ntipopullor, **d**epolarizim, **d**epopullim, **d**emilitarizim, **p**annjerëzor, **i**nterkontinental, **i**ntermolekular, **m**ultimilioner, **e**kstravagante etc.

Suffixation (prejardhja prapashtesore) in Albanian

A suffix is an affix placed after the stem of a word. Suffixation is the most productive way of creating new words. Suffixes in Albanian are about three times in quantity than prefixes. Some of the suffixes in Albanian are:

-ar, -ës, -tar, -ist, -im, -smi, -je, -i, -si, -ri, -or, -tor, -ak, -as, -am, -it, -iot.

The common nouns created by the suffixes: *-ar, -tar, -tore, -ore, -ës, -or*

Gjuhëtar, kosovar, shqiptar, këngëtar, arsimtar, harkëtar, gazetar, arkëtar, shkrimtar, kopshtar, udhëtare, dritare, ëmbëltores, floktore, akulllore, fushore, kripore, lugore, bregore, fajtor, arsimor, drejtor, nxënës, gjykatës, shitës, shkelës, ndihmës, tërheqës, udhëheqës.

The suffixes –im, -ishte, -je, -ik, -ësi, -ëm, -ak, an, -i

Dekretim, ndalim, interpretim, kontraktim, përdorim, vendim, lulishte, barishte, hekurishte, veshje, ruajtje, hyrje, njohje, diplomatik, madhësi, drejtësi, bashkësi, mundësi, aftësi, lexueshëm, punueshëm, ulqiank, durrsak, zezak, vezak, pejan, kuksian, njohuri, pasuri, lumturi, shprehi, bukuri, gjallëri, zejтари, përgjegjësi, dituri, blegtori, befasi.

During the suffixation process in Albanian, the word has some phonetic changes, the final vowel of the root is removed e.g. *luftë- (luft-oj), majtë – (majt-as), kërkësë (kërk-oj), vepër- (vepr-oj), vulë – (vul-os)*. On the other hand, there are cases when a vowel is added to support the new word. E.g. *Mal – (mal-ë-si), lajm (lajm-ë-tar)*.

From suffixation are formed nouns, adjectives, verbs, adverbs etc. Suffixation changes the grammatical and lexical class of the word.

The formation of nouns: i bukur – bukuri, çel – çelës, gënje – gënjeshtër

The formation of adjectives: ar – i artë, bukurosh – i bukur, sot – i sotëm

The formation of verbs: punë- punoj, i lirë- liroj, zbardh- zbardhoj, larg – largoj

The formation of adverbs: vazhdim – vazhdimisht, krejt- krejtësisht, serioz- seriozisht.

There are also some foreign suffixes that are assimilated from the time in Albanian language. E.g. *-ist, -izëm, -azh, -al*.

Arbitraritet (arbitrar), traktorist (traktor), anarkizëm (anarki), industrial (industri), majtizëm (i majtë), djathtizëm (i djathtë), zyrtarizëm (zyrtar), majtist (i majtë).

There are some words with two suffixes, E.g.

Burrë–burrëri–burrërisht, trim–trimëri–trimërisht, miq–miqësi–miqësisht, urtë–urtësi–urtësisht, detyrë–detyrim–detyrimisht, nder–ndershmëri–ndershmërisht, fshat–fshatar–fshatarak.

Prejardhje parashteso-prapashtesore

Except the word formation through suffixes or prefixes, there are some words that possess both of them; they are made of prefixes and suffixes together.

Some examples with new words made of prefixes and suffixes:

Ndërgjyqës, përfundoj, përgenjeshtror, përvetësoj, përfaqësoj, shfrytëzoj, zhdoganoj, zbukuroj, nguros, pagjumësi, meditje, etc.

Conclusion

Affixation as a word formation process is very important in English and Albanian in creating new words from the existing ones. Prefixation, suffixation and infixation are all known as affixation. Affixation is a word formation process of making new words by adding affixes to the root or base word.

Prefixation was adding morphemes to the beginning of the root, while suffixation was defined as adding bound morphemes at the end of a stem. Infixation was inserting affixes within the word. Infixation cases are rare in comparison with prefixation and suffixation.

According to the last researches, one third of the affixations are prefixes and most of them are suffixes that are also more productive than the rest.

In this study, were described all the types of affixation in both languages with examples and definitions. There was also made a contrastive and a comparative analysis between affixes in English and in Albanian, what are the similarities and differences in both of them, based on previous studies and letting others make further research on this topic.

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